

CLASSIFIED ASPECTS OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE FINANCIAL ACTIVITY OF INSURANCE COMPANIES

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Abstract. This scientific thesis describes the scientific basis and necessity of regulating the activities of insurance companies. Classification features of internal and external factors influencing the activity of insurance companies are described. In international practice, studies have been carried out on the main directions of state regulation of the insurance system.

Keywords: insurance, financial instrument, investment, deposits, capital, financial stability, insurance reserves, norms, financial risk.

In the analysis of financial stability indicators of insurance companies, it is important to classify the external and internal factors affecting it and reveal their main features. Factors affecting the financial stability of insurance companies can be divided into external (uncontrollable) and internal (controllable) factors according to the general approach (Figure 1).

It should be noted that one of the main external factors affecting the financial stability of insurance companies is the legal basis of regulation of this system in the country. It is precisely the fact that the legal and regulatory documents of the regulation of the insurance market are developed at a perfect level that ensures the efficient operation of companies based on the implementation of strategic projects,

optimal decision-making, and the achievement of financial stability. In addition, as the main internal factors affecting the financial stability of insurance companies, it is possible to mention such important factors as the effective organization of the corporate governance mechanism in insurance companies, the possibilities of diversification of insurance types and services, the correct organization of risk management, the optimization of the insurance portfolio, the amount of insurance reserves. Based on the main idea that "in order to get an idea about the financial stability of insurance companies, there are no clearly defined quantitative financial indicators, but these indicators can be differentiated based on several characteristics of the insurance company", it is appropriate to analyze financial stability indicators in a separate sequence is considered

Solvency of insurance companies means the ability of the policyholder to fully fulfill monetary obligations on time in accordance with the terms agreed with the contract or legal documents. Determining the solvency of insurance companies is based on the characteristics of their sector and industry. In addition, there are special features of this indicator in international standards of financial reporting and international practice. In particular, in accordance with the regulations adopted in the European Union countries, the solvency of insurance companies is evaluated by comparing the current situation with the standard amount (norm) determined by the solvency.

1 Picture. Classification of factors affecting the financial stability of insurance companies¹

In general, the level of solvency of an insurance company should answer the question of how much private capital is sufficient for the company to fulfill its obligations. Another important group of indicators representing the financial

¹ Муалиф томонидан тузилган.

stability of insurance companies are liquidity ratios. The liquidity ratio determines the ability of the insurance company to meet its short-term obligations during the reporting year and to cover current expenses related to losses or insurance policy payments. Assessing the financial stability of insurance companies is one of the important tasks for all participants in the financial market. The financial stability of insurance companies is a difficult process to assess only within certain indicators. Therefore, as we noted above, in the assessment of financial stability indicators, it is necessary to take into account all external and internal factors, in addition to financial coefficients.

Today, although a regulatory document has been developed to assess the efficiency of joint-stock companies with a state share in the authorized capital, the provisions of this Regulation are not applied to commercial banks and insurance companies. In our opinion, a regulation based on international standards and international rating agencies' calculation methodology should be developed and put into practice for assessing the efficiency and financial stability of insurance companies. As a result of this, there is an opportunity to further increase the attractiveness of investors along with the development of the competitive environment among insurance companies.

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